

Strong Core, Better Score? Investigating Core Strength and Handwriting Skills in Adolescents

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Received: Jun 25, 2025

Accepted: July 24, 2025

Published: July 26, 2025

Abstract-

Background: Handwriting is a complex motor skill requiring fine motor control, postural stability, and upper limb coordination. Core strength provides proximal stability, which is essential for efficient and controlled distal movements involved in handwriting.

Objective: To investigate the correlation between core muscle strength and handwriting speed in adolescents.

Methods: This observational study involved adolescent participants who underwent the McGill Core Endurance Test to assess core strength and the Brown–Fox Handwriting Speed Test to evaluate handwriting performance. The correlation between core strength and handwriting speed was analyzed statistically.

Results: The findings revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between core muscle strength and handwriting speed. These results are supported by previous studies, which emphasize the role of trunk stability in enhancing upper extremity motor function and control.

Conclusion: Enhanced core muscle strength is associated with better handwriting performance, suggesting that core strengthening exercises may benefit students by improving postural control and upper limb function. Future studies should explore this relationship through interventional designs with larger sample sizes and more standardized handwriting measures.

Keywords: Core strength, handwriting speed, adolescents, trunk stability, McGill test, Brown-Fox handwriting test.

Introduction- Core stability is defined as the ability to control trunk position and movement to optimize the generation, transfer, and absorption of forces through the body [1]. It acts as the foundation for most functional movements, serving a central role in posture and dynamic motion. The core has often been conceptualized as a box formed by the abdominal muscles at the front, the paraspinal and gluteal muscles at the back, the diaphragm on the top, and the pelvic floor and hip girdle muscles at the base. This region works as a coordinated unit, providing a stable base for limb movement and facilitating efficient biomechanical functioning [2].

The benefits of core strengthening are well documented across various clinical and athletic populations. Research has shown that improving core endurance can help reduce low back pain, enhance upper limb function in breast cancer survivors, improve mobility post-total knee and hip arthroplasty, and even boost athletic performance [2]. Despite this evidence, the potential relationship between core strength and fine motor tasks such as handwriting remains relatively unexplored. Although some research has emphasized how trunk stability can influence skilled upper limb tasks [3], specific connections to handwriting speed—particularly among adolescents—have not been sufficiently addressed.

Handwriting is a complex perceptual-motor task that involves precise coordination between the musculoskeletal and nervous systems [4]. It relies on the integration of multiple components including fine motor control, visual-motor coordination, proprioceptive awareness, and postural stability. Effective handwriting requires the manipulation of a writing tool with coordinated movements of the fingers, wrist, elbow, and shoulder, which are, in turn, supported by a stable trunk. The trunk provides postural control necessary to allow distal precision and fine control. If the trunk is unstable, compensatory movements can arise, leading to fatigue, reduced legibility, and slower writing speeds [5].

Handwriting speed is especially important in academic contexts, as it affects students' ability to complete exams, take notes, and express ideas effectively. Greater handwriting speed not only increases the efficiency of written communication but also reduces the cognitive load on working memory, allowing students to focus more on content than motor execution [6]. Studies have shown that transcription speed is directly related to academic performance and writing quality in school-aged children [7]. Inadequate handwriting speed can disadvantage students during timed exams, causing an underestimation of their academic potential [8].

Although handwriting is often assumed to be a distal motor skill, the importance of proximal stability—especially trunk stability—is increasingly recognized. The shoulder girdle serves as the anchor point for forearm and hand movements, and effective force transmission from the core facilitates more controlled and sustained upper limb activity [2]. Postural endurance allows the body to maintain an upright seated position during writing tasks, reducing muscular fatigue and supporting better writing mechanics. This further highlights the need to study how core

strength may contribute to handwriting performance, especially in the adolescent population, where rapid musculoskeletal changes are taking place.

Adolescence, defined as the age range from 10 to 24 years, is a critical period marked by growth spurts, hormonal changes, and neuromuscular maturation [11]. These physiological changes can impact postural control, endurance, and fine motor coordination. Understanding how core muscle function interacts with writing ability during this formative stage can be valuable in both educational and rehabilitation contexts. A better understanding could inform interventions aimed at improving handwriting speed and quality through physical training and postural control exercises.

Despite the rise of digital technology, handwriting remains a vital skill, particularly in childhood and adolescence, where it plays a key role in motor and cognitive development [13]. It is a complex process involving fine motor control, where distal joints like the wrist and fingers produce writing, while proximal joints like the shoulder and elbow provide support and stability [14].

Core stability, defined as the ability to control trunk position and movement, is essential for maintaining posture and enabling precise upper limb function. It relies on coordinated activation of trunk muscles and neuromuscular control to support limb movements [1,15,16]. Improved core strength may thus enhance handwriting by providing a stable base for fine motor tasks.

One of the most reliable ways to assess core endurance is through the **McGill Core Endurance Tests**, which consist of four isometric endurance tests: the trunk flexor test, extensor test, and right and left side bridge tests. These tests have shown strong reliability in assessing core muscle function [17]. For example, Waldhelm and Li (2012) showed that these endurance tests are highly reliable for evaluating core muscle strength. Similarly, studies by Esfahani et al. [18] also support their use in populations with and without back pain.

Meanwhile, handwriting speed is commonly assessed by having individuals copy a standard sentence containing all the letters of the alphabet—"The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog"—as many times as possible in two minutes [9]. This method is objective and easy to administer in school settings. Legible handwriting and speed are not only indicators of academic readiness but also influence a child's self-worth and classroom participation [10, 12].

Despite widespread evidence supporting both the importance of core strength and the significance of handwriting speed in education, there remains a noticeable gap in literature addressing a possible correlation between the two. No known studies have examined whether stronger core muscles are associated with faster handwriting speed among adolescents.

This study, therefore, aims to investigate this underexplored relationship by examining the **correlation between core muscle endurance and handwriting speed in adolescents aged 14–18 years**. By assessing core strength using the McGill Endurance Tests and handwriting speed through a standard sentence-copying task, this research seeks to uncover whether improving core stability could serve as a potential strategy to enhance academic performance via improved fine motor function.

Objectives

1. **Primary Objective:**

To observe the correlation between core muscle endurance and handwriting speed as a fine motor skill in school-going adolescents aged 14–18 years.

2. **Secondary Objective:**

To increase awareness of the importance of core muscle strengthening exercises among adolescents, particularly in relation to fine motor and academic performance.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting- This was a cross-sectional observational study conducted at Adarsh Madhya Vidyalay (Utkramit), K Nagar, Purnia, Bihar, over a period of six months. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of NIMS University, Jaipur, Rajasthan. Permission was granted by the school authorities, and informed consent was obtained from all participants and their guardians.

Participants and Sampling- A total of 60 school-going adolescents, aged between 14 and 18 years, were recruited using a convenient sampling method. Inclusion criteria consisted of healthy male and female students within the specified age range who were cooperative and willing to participate. Students were excluded if they had any systemic illness, hand injury, were uncooperative, or were menstruating at the time of testing.

Materials Used- A4-size lined paper, Standardized black ball pen, Pencil and eraser, Mat for floor-based testing, Stopwatch

Procedure- After initial screening for eligibility based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, baseline demographic data were recorded using a structured case proforma. Two assessments were carried out: (1) Core muscle endurance, and (2) Handwriting speed.

1. Core Muscle Endurance Assessment

Core strength was evaluated using the McGill Core Endurance Test Battery [15,16], which includes:

Isometric Abdominal Test: In a supine position with knees bent at 90°, participants curled the trunk to a marked distance and maintained the position isometrically. Duration held determined the grade from 0 (no contraction) to 5 (scapulae clearing the table with hands behind head for 20–30 seconds) [15].

Isometric Internal/External Abdominal Oblique Test: Performed in supine lying, the participant reached across the body to touch the opposite side while maintaining proper breathing and posture. Grading was based on position and endurance time (0–5 scale) [15,16].

Dynamic Horizontal Side Support (Side Bridge Test): This test assessed the endurance of the quadratus lumborum. Participants performed a side-bridge with either bent or extended knees, and the duration of proper hold determined the score [15].

Isometric Extensor Test: Conducted in prone position to assess the endurance of the erector spinae and multifidus muscles. Grading ranged from 0 (no movement) to 5 (full extension with hands behind the head and chest/ribs off the mat) [15].

All tests were explained and demonstrated prior to performance, and appropriate rest intervals were provided between tests to avoid fatigue-related bias.

2. Handwriting Speed Assessment

Handwriting speed was measured using the Brown Fox Handwriting Speed Test [13]. Each participant was given two minutes to copy the sentence “The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog” repeatedly on lined A4 paper using the same pen. The number of correctly written words was counted at the end of the time to determine handwriting speed in words per minute.

Result- The experimental results are shown in the Table 1. The total no. of study population for this study was 60, in which the highest no. subjects[n=20] participated in the study were of age group 15 years. [33.33%]. 26.67% of the subjects were of age group 14 years[n=16]. In the age group of 16 years there were 23.33 % subject participated[n=14]. Only 11.67 % [n=7] of the population participated in the study where as the no. of 18 years of age group were least [n=3] which constituted the 5% of the total population

Age (In Yrs.)	n = 60	In %
14 Yrs.	16	26.67%
15 Yrs.	20	33.33%
16 Yrs.	14	23.33%
17 Yrs.	7	11.67%
18 Yrs.	3	5.00%

Table 1: Frequency distribution of age of subjects

Frequency distribution of gender of subjects is shown in table 2. Female participants were more than male. Total no. of female population included 33 and male population remained 27.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of gender of subjects

Gender	n = 60	In %
Male	27	45.00%
Female	33	55.00%

The frequency distribution of Isometric abdominal test grade of subjects is shown in table 3. The no. of subjects for normal grading (5) were highest[n=29] in which the hands were kept behind neck, until scapulae clear table (20 to 30 second hold). No. of subjects for grading good (4) remained second highest[n=27] in which Arms crossed over chest, until scapulae clear table (15 to 20 second hold). 6.67 % of the total population remained for fair grading [n=4]. No subjects fell in the category of poor and trace grading.

Table 3: Frequency distribution of isometric abdominal test grade of subjects

Isometric abdominal test	n = 60	In %
Normal	29	48.33%
good	27	45.00%
Fair	4	6.67%
Poor	0	0.00%
Trace	0	0.00%

Frequency distribution of isometric internal/external abdominal oblique test grade of subjects is shown in table 4. The no. of subjects was highest in normal grading[n=35]. 33.33% of the subjects [n=20] fell under the category of good grading. Fair grading constituted the 8.33% of the population[n=5]. No subjects fell under the grading of poor and trace.

Table 4: Frequency distribution of isometric internal/external abdominal oblique test grade of subjects

Isometric internal/external abdominal oblique test	n = 60	In %
Normal	35	58.33%
Good	20	33.33%
Fair	5	8.33%
Poor	0	0.00%
Trace	0	0.00%

Frequency distribution of dynamic horizontal side support grade of subjects is shown in table 5. 48.33% of the total population [n=29] had shown the Normal grading which is highest. 31.67% of the population [n=19] shown the good grading. 20 % of the subjects [n= 12] fell under the category of fair grading. No subjects were found for poor and trace grading.

Table 5: Frequency distribution of dynamic horizontal side support grade of subjects

Dynamic horizontal side support	n = 60	In %
Normal	29	48.33%
Good	19	31.67%
Fair	12	20.00%
Poor	0	0.00%
Trace	0	0.00%

Frequency distribution of isometric extensor test grade of subjects is shown in table 6. 66.67% subject of the population had shown Normal grading [n=40]. Good grading individuals [n=12] contributed for 20 % of the total population. 13.33 % of the population fell for Fair grading [n=8]. No subjects were found for Poor and Trace grading.

Table 6: Frequency distribution of isometric extensor test grade of subjects

Isometric extensor test	n = 60	In %
Normal	40	66.67%
Good	12	20.00%
Fair	8	13.33%
Poor	0	0.00%
Trace	0	0.00%

Frequency distribution of hand writing speed of subjects is shown in table 7. 31.67 % subject of the population [n=19] had written no. of words in the range of 31-40. 23.33 % of the population [n=14] had handwriting speed in the range of 41-50 words per minute. 20% of the population [n=12] had hand writing speed in the range of 31-40 words per minute. 15 % of the population [n=9] had handwriting speed in the range of 61-70 words per minute, which is the highest. Lastly, the 10% of the population [n=6] had hand writing speed less than 30 words per minute, which is least.

Table 7: Frequency distribution of hand writing speed of subjects

Hand writing speed	n = 60	In %
≤ 30	6	10.00%
31 - 40	12	20.00%
41 - 50	14	23.33%
51 - 60	19	31.67%
61 - 70	9	15.00%

Descriptive statistics of age and hand writing speed of subjects have shown in table 8. The age group taken in the study is of adolescent i.e., of 14-18 years. The median of the age is 15. No. of words per minute ranges from 18 – 67. The median of hand writing speed i.e., no. of words per minute is 48.5. The mean with standard deviation is shown in table 8.

Table 8: Descriptive statistics of age and hand writing speed of subjects

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Median (IQR)	Mean ± SD
Age	14	18	15 (14-16)	15.35 ± 1.147
Hand writing speed	18	67	48.5 (38.75-56.25)	47.4 ± 12.592

Finally, the correlation between core muscle strength and hand writing speed of subjects by using Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient is shown in table 9. The value of correlation coefficient of all the variable has been obtained negative as shown in the table 9. P- value

Of variable Isometric abdominal test is 0.00001.p – value of Isometric Internal/External Abdominal Oblique Test is 0.000010. p- value of Dynamic Horizontal Side Support is 0.0001. Lastly, the p- value of isometric extensor test is 0.00002 which shows the significant result and establish correlation between core muscle strength and handwriting speed.

Table 9: Correlation between core muscle strength and hand writing speed of subjects by using Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient

Variables	Corr (r)	t-test	P - Value	Significance
Isometric Abdominal Test	-0.561	-5.166	0.00001	All are significant
Isometric Internal/External Abdominal Oblique Test	-0.480	-4.164	0.00010	
Dynamic Horizontal Side Support	-0.609	-5.845	0.00001	
Isometric extensor test	-0.521	-4.647	0.00002	

Discussion- In this study, McGill Core Endurance Test and Brown-Forsythe Handwriting Speed Test were used to assess core strength and handwriting speed, respectively. The results indicated a significant positive correlation between core muscle strength and handwriting performance.

Miyake et al. investigated the effects of core exercises on upper extremity skilled motor behavior and postural control, reporting significant improvements in post-intervention scores in the core exercise group compared to control. They concluded that enhanced trunk stability facilitates upper extremity motor control, suggesting that trunk plays a foundational role in transmitting motion and stability to distal segments [2].

Jha and Nuhmani evaluated a five-week core stability training program in collegiate athletes and found improvements in upper quarter Y-balance and functional throwing performance. Their study supports the idea that core stabilization enhances upper limb performance [1].

Shih-Lin et al. emphasized that trunk core muscle contraction increases intra-abdominal pressure, contributing to postural stability and stiffness essential for seated activities such as writing [3].

Esfahani et al. described how core stability allows for the efficient production and transfer of force, playing a critical role in coordinated trunk and limb movement [19]. Their findings align with those of Hodges and Richardson, who showed that core stabilizers (e.g., transversus abdominis, multifidus) activate prior to limb movements—supporting the proximal-to-distal model of motor control [31].

In handwriting, although the forearm is primarily responsible for movement, shoulder and trunk stability serve as a postural anchor, and poor posture or weak musculature can affect handwriting output [5].

El-Nashar and El-Wishy studied hemiparetic stroke patients and concluded that core muscle training improved both upper limb function and trunk balance, further indicating the importance of core strength in upper limb performance [12].

In rhythmic gymnasts, Estebian-Gracia et al. demonstrated that a 12-week core training program led to enhanced trunk strength, better body composition, and increased EMG activity of core muscles—directly impacting performance in skill-based activities [13].

For assessment reliability, Esfahani, Rezaeian, and Dommerholt verified that two repetitions of the McGill tests are sufficient to evaluate core endurance reliably in individuals with and without nonspecific low back pain [20].

Gokulakrishnan and Franklin conducted a prospective interventional study where participants performed upper limb strengthening exercises for four weeks. The results revealed significant increases in handwriting speed (from 133.8 to 142.7 wpm) and grip strength (from 24.33 kg to 40.96 kg), indicating that upper limb and forearm strengthening directly improves handwriting speed [5].

Together, these studies support the hypothesis that increased core strength contributes to better handwriting speed, likely due to improved trunk stability, posture, and coordinated upper limb movement.

LIMITATIONS

Small sample size, Observational design limits causality inference, More reliable and validated outcome tools for handwriting speed can be used.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

Increase sample size in future studies, Convert observational design to interventional design, Use gold-standard outcome measures for handwriting speed assessment.

Conclusion- This study highlights a significant positive correlation between core muscle strength and handwriting speed, indicating that improved trunk stability may contribute to enhanced upper limb motor performance. As supported by previous literature, core stability plays a vital role in maintaining posture, generating proximal support, and enabling controlled distal movements—factors crucial for tasks like handwriting. These findings suggest that incorporating core strengthening exercises may be a beneficial strategy in educational and rehabilitative settings to improve handwriting performance, especially among students or individuals with upper limb coordination challenges. Further interventional studies with larger sample sizes and standardized outcome tools are recommended to establish causality and validate these findings.

Author contribution-

- Conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work: JS
- Drafting the work or reviewing it critically for important intellectual content: RJ, JS
- Final approval of the version to be published: JS
- Accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved: RJ

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank all coauthors for their work.

Funding- None

Conflict of interest

We do not have any conflict of interest.

Ethical approval

The protocol was approved by ethical committee of Nims university IRB. (NIMS PTOT/Ethical/March/2024/04

Data availability statement

We confirm that the data supporting the findings of the study will be shared upon reasonable request.

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